

DELIVERABLE 6.3

Social Impact Assessment

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Abbreviations

BLISS: Blended Lifecycle Integrated Social System Framework

BM: Business Model

BPA: Bisphenol A

CAN: Covalent Adaptable Network

C2C: Cradle to Cradle

CFRC: Carbon fiber-reinforced composite

DBA: Dibutylamine

DCM: Dichloromethane

EC: European Commission

E-LCA: Environmental Life Cycle Assessment

GWP: Global Warming Potential

SEIA: Socio Economic Impact Assessment

LCA: Life-Cycle Assessment

OECD: Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development

PP: Polypropylene

PRP: Performance reference point

PSILCA: Product social impact life cycle assessment

RTM: Resin Transfer Moulding

scCO₂: Supercritical CO₂

SIA: Social Impact Assessment

S-LCA: Social Life Cycle Assessment

sLCIA: Social Life Cycle Impact Assessment

SVOCs: Semi-volatile organic chemicals

SSbD: Safe and Sustainable by Design

TEA: Techno-Economic Assessment

TRL: Technology Readiness Level

VOCs: Volatile organic chemicals

WP: Work Packages

Zn(acac)₂: Zinc Acetylacetonate

Executive Summary

This deliverable is about an ex-ante **Social Lifecycle Assessment (S-LCA)** of an epoxy resin reinforced by hemp fibres (referred to as ESTELLA epoxy resin in this document) in comparison to a 100% fossil epoxy resin as carbon fiber-reinforced composite (CFRC) in the frame of the EU funded research project ESTELLA.

Social Impact Assessment for (Bioeconomy) products faces challenges as it is mostly linked to (techno)economic aspects. In addition, there exists no universally accepted definition of social impact and social impact assessment of the biobased economy yet.

Moreover, ESTELLA focuses on **early-stage technology developments**, but according to our literature research there are no studies known which have developed a specific and easily adaptable ex-ante S-LCA methodology to assess the socio-economic impacts of new and emerging technologies over the full product life cycle yet.

Therefore, Social Impact Assessment, especially for early-stage technology developments, remains a challenge.

In order to cope with this challenge, ESTELLA applied a concise assessment methodology based on Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment (Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment for Decision-Making; Life Cycle Initiative) and on the participatory approach in S-LCA mentioned by (Mathe (2014)) for performing an ex-ante and cradle-to-gate S-LCA.

By doing so, we integrated research results linked to WP 2-6 and literature review results (for input on E-LCA) as well as stakeholder views.

But still, our ex-ante S-LCA of the ESTELLA epoxy resin is facing certain **limitations:**

- Lack of quantitative data especially from E-LCA and e.g. uncertainty about toxic effects due to early-stage technology development,
- Variety of techno-economic assumptions, especially due to upscaling and recycling uncertainties on larger scale,
- Variety of interrelations of impact categories and uncertainty in terms of trade-offs, which account especially for a) environmental effects as they depend on the kind of biomass and amount of biobased material and processing technology used and b) land use as this depends on the biomass quantity and kind of land under cultivation,

- Limited engagement of stakeholder groups esp. from value chain actors (industry) and consumers due to early-stage technology development.

Nevertheless, this analysis can serve as **approximation** for potential future social impacts of the ESTELLA epoxy resin.

In this respect, our results highlight **three** potential **social hotspots**, out of them **one** potential **social risk** by the usage of BPA as precursor in the ESTELLA resin and **two** potential **social benefits** in view of *recycling* and *up-scaling potential*.

Thus, future research focus should be laid on the improvement of upscaling and recycling processes as both are not yet efficient and sustainable enough.

In this regard, **social benefits** of the ESTELLA epoxy resin can be achieved, especially if:

- A **higher recycling rate** of the ESTELLA epoxy resin (preferably from recycled or biobased content from local biowaste sources) will be realized with impact on:
 - i. Lowering the CO₂eq-emissions increased carbon uptake;
 - ii. Lowering landfilling or incineration of toxic waste;
- A **further upscale** will be realized using standard industrial processes (e.g. state-of-the-art RTM technology) with impact on:
 - i. Market uptake and spill-over effects;
 - ii. Cost reduction by economies of scale.

Thus, in order to reach wider social acceptance, **further research** is necessary:

- Develop a 100% biobased epoxy resin from preferably non-food biomass;
- Reduce toxic effects on human health by substitution of BPA by biobased materials e.g. epoxidized vegetable oils and of succinic acid/anhydride and SVOC/VOC by usage of bio-based succinic acid/anhydride and less organic compounds (VOCs and SVOCs) incl. solvent recovery having a positive effect on human health and environment;
- Usage of renewable energy, recycled material and less-cost intensive processing (e.g. alternative for Zn(acac)₂ as catalyst) for further cost savings;
- Reduce effects on land use when producing hemp by focussing on marginal areas;

- Create transparency by applying and communicating sustainability standards and principles (e.g. in terms of CO₂ reduction);
- Install co-creation processes involving all relevant stakeholder groups, offering participation and inclusiveness in the decision-making process;
- Built up regional/local supply chains to create “value for value” chain actors.

By this, spill-over effects can be achieved, increasing the market uptake in other market segments as well, contributing a green transition of the economy and overall well-being.

1 Goals of the study

The Goal of the study is about performing an ex-ante **S-LCA** of thermoset composites which are recyclable in the frame of **ESTELLA** project from cradle-to gate.

ESTELLA stands for “*DESIGN of bio-based Thermoset polymer with rECycling capability by dynAmic bonds for bio-composite manufacturing*” and is an EU funded Research project, running from 2022 to 2025, with the aim to design novel bio-based epoxy resins with inherent recyclability capabilities.¹

When performing an impact assessment it is all about to analyze, evaluate and manage the intended and unintended positive and negative consequences of planned interventions (Rodrigues and Rituerto 2022). Although impact assessment is mainly linked to techno-economic aspects, major efforts have been made to consider social aspects over the last years as well. The reason for this is the emergence of sustainable development issues which were triggered by the definition of 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) by the UN in 2015 laid down in its Agenda 2030 (European Commission).

The Agenda 2030 balances the three dimensions of sustainable development: economic, social and environmental. For implementing the Agenda 2030 the UN stresses the need for strengthening the social dimension of sustainable development (United Nations, (2015)). Also, the European Commission (EC) lays efforts on sustaining and improving the quality of life of its citizens. In this sense, among the priorities of the EC for the period 2024-2029 are to promote social fairness, strengthen social and regional cohesion, and ensure equal opportunities for all (European Commission, (2024)).

In this sense, there is a high need to strengthen social impact assessment of activities or interventions during and after their implementation to minimize the cost to the society while maximizing the benefits (Stephen Appiah Takyi, (2014)).

However, along Rafiaani et al. (2018) and Rodrigues and Rituerto (2022) due to the fact that impact assessment is mostly linked to (techno)economic aspects, there exists no universally accepted definition of social impact and social impact assessment of the biobased economy.

Emerging or new technologies are characterized among others by their uncertainty and ambiguity (Rodrigues and Rituerto 2022), which makes a Social Impact Assessment even more difficult as they have to be done ex-ante.

¹ [ESTELLA PROJECT | ESTELLA PROJECT](#)

In this respect, recently studies – mainly linked to E-LCA - have attempted to develop a specific and easily adaptable methodology to ex-ante assess the socio-economic impacts of new and emerging technologies.

A similar ex-ante approach is still missing for S-LCA methodologies covering the full product life cycle (cradle-to-cradle).

In order to cope with these preconditions, we adopted a concise cradle-to-gate S-LCA methodology in order to best evaluate the causality between the intervention and its impacts ex-ante.

As 100% biobased epoxy resin could not match ESTELLAs' purposes, ESTELLA selected out of the range of epoxy resins and reinforcements the best combinations, which are:

- An **epoxy resin associative CAN reinforced by hemp fibers which is recyclable**

and

- An **epoxy resin with associative CAN reinforced by lignocellulose nanofibers from Eucalyptus which is recyclable.**

As benchmark epoxy resin serves a **carbon fiber-reinforced composite** (CFRC) which is 100% fossil based, not recyclable and therefore landfilled.

The results described in this Deliverable 6.3 are linked to the epoxy resin enforced with hemp fibers (**BPA based epoxy resin with associative CAN reinforced by hemp fibers**) and are based on **quantitative data** from WP 2-6, from **literature** and on **qualitative data** from stakeholder feedback.

The second epoxy resin reinforced by lignocellulose nanofibers from Eucalyptus of ESTELLA is not covered by this Deliverable.

The reasons for this exclusion are based on specific research results achieved for this epoxy resin in the ESTELLA project:

- The heterogeneity of fibres from lignin results in uneven and modest properties, whereas hemp fiber provides comparable strength to traditional synthetic fibers like glass (Del. 4.4 and Del. 2.4);
- Due to the chemical structure of lignin fibers their value-added applications are severely limited whereas hemp fibers show huge potential for multidirectional applications (Del. 6.4);
- Less recycling potential of nanofibers due to their stronger crosslink networks (nanofibers could not be effectively separated from the residual resin) (Del. 4.4);
- Limited scaling potential as the mechanical properties through the acid treatment during the dissolution of the lignin-based epoxy resin are deteriorated even by using self-healing properties of the materials the original shape of the epoxy resin could not be restored

(less thermal and mechanical properties after recycling) resulting in less higher value usage (Del. 2.4, Del. 4.2 and Del. 4.3);

- Higher environmental footprint for the production of nanocellulose fibers due to significantly higher water usage, higher energy input and chemical usage. Higher amount of chemicals and heavy metals content found in fibers; and higher negative impact on biodiversity if not stemming from waste lignocellulosic biomass (Del. 5.4 and Del. 6.4);
- Additional toxic chemicals are used (DCM) for dissolving lignin (Del. 5.3).

Nevertheless, we included further findings from literature in terms of a risk-benefit-analysis for the **epoxy resin reinforced by lignocellulose nanofibers** in this deliverable in chapter 6.

The methodology and approach of the Social Impact Assessment of the selected epoxy resin are described in the following chapters:

In Chapter 2 is capturing definitions for social impact and Social Impact Assessment, chapter 3 describes methodologies for Social Impact Assessment, chapter 4 is about Social Impact Assessment in the bioeconomy and in chapter 5 the methodological approach for doing a Social Impact Assessment in the frame of ESTELLA is given, Chapter 6 is about interpretation of results achieved.

2 Definitory framework

2.1 Definition of social impact

Along Vanclay (2012), **social impact** is all about planned interventions that affect or concern people either directly or indirectly.

Although there is a need to strengthen the social development, a clear consensual definition of the concept of social impact is still lacking. While the social sciences look at the impact of policies and programs, often in terms of social progress, social investors tend to look for the non-financial (that is, social and environmental) returns on their investments, which they tend to quantify and/or express in monetary terms, if possible. For achieving social and in a wider sense sustainability goals **impact measurement** is crucial. Nevertheless, it is often difficult to quantify impacts European Parliament (2017).

The key challenges of impact assessment have been summarized by the European Court of Auditors (2008) as follows: “...*attribution problems, timing problems (the time lag before impacts appear), the causality problem, measurement problems*”. The latter relates to issues of data availability and suitable indicators, the comparability of results, aggregation, but above all the need to understand dynamics properly and take them into account in evaluations (Bührer et al.(2022).

- Thus, social impact measurement and management methodologies and approaches have to be designed which are tailored to the context in which they are used, as there is no one-size-fits-all approach. Therefore, the European Union and the OECD have jointly produced an important study called “*Measure, manage and maximize your impact. A guide for a social economy*” in 2024 (European Commission (2024). The guide outlines six building blocks that structure a social impact management system. These building blocks are: Integrating impact evidence into decision-making,
- Engaging stakeholders,
- Developing skills,
- Exploring digital tools for data collection, storage and visualization,
- Seeking independent valuation,
- Establishing a permanent action plan to follow up on learnings.

Moreover, this guide qualifies “economic prosperity”, “employment”, “social inclusion”, “well-being” and “community” as the most important impact areas for the social economy.

2.2 Definition of social impact indicators

Indicators are measurable information used for the assessment. They should be selected on a case-by-case basis. Sources could include legal, policy or technical documentation on socio-economic impacts.

All indicators should be applied to “RACER” criteria (European Commission (2005):

- **R**elvant, closely linked to the objectives to be reached.
- **A**ccepted by stakeholders and users.
- **C**redible for non-experts, unambiguous and easy to interpret.
- **E**asy to monitor.
- **R**obust against manipulation.

Social impact indicators are important for evaluating the success of efforts aimed at social improvements. They are the building blocks for measuring and analysing outcomes. These indicators entail dimensions like economic development, education, health, and environmental sustainability.

Due to the lack of harmonized approach for S-LCA, there exist different sets of social indicators:

- The OECD (2024) defined a preliminary set of social indicators for social enterprises for each impact area. Indicators can be applied to different levels like outputs, outcome and impact (see [Table 1](#)).

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Table 1: Potential indicators for social economy linked to outcomes

	OUTCOMES	EXAMPLES OF INDICATORS
ECONOMIC PROSPERITY AND EMPLOYMENT	Equitable distribution of income	Facilitated access to job opportunities; access to finance; access to capacity-building; reduction in income inequalities and job positions across different groups
	Household welfare	Reported improvements in investments in housing, health, education, and the quantity and quality of meals eaten
	Economic empowerment of women and disadvantaged groups	Reported improvements in income earned; women's active role in important household decisions
	Skill development	Increased exposure to the world of work for vulnerable groups; training and apprenticeships; progress on soft and hard skills
	Job quality	Compliance with decent work standards; stable work; safety at work; reduced absenteeism; perceived opportunities; work-life balance; career trajectories; new leadership roles; diversity within an industry; representation of leadership
	Labour-market inclusion	Net change in employment directly attributed to social economy entities within disadvantaged groups; speed of hiring vulnerable groups; self-employment
	Resilience to economic shocks and risks	Survival rates of social economy entities; financial resilience of women and disadvantaged groups (e.g., reported improvements in ability to plan finances, ability to save money)
	Development of local trade and production	Reliance on local producers and suppliers versus outsourcing (establishment of local networks, increased number of local partnerships); smaller environmental footprint from economic activity
	Systems change	Emergence or improvement of national or local policies in support of the social economy and social entrepreneurship; growing number of social economy entrepreneurs and organisations; establishment of new collaborations with other social economy, private and public actors; evidence of mainstream businesses moving towards sustainable corporate practices through partnerships with the social economy
SOCIAL INCLUSION	Existence and extent of democratic governance practices	Presence and diversity of stakeholder groups on boards; invitation to and attendance at operational, governance and evaluation meetings
	Participatory management	Voting rights; participation in planning, measurement, delivery, etc.; collective bargaining practices; opportunities to voice concerns and ideas
	Experience and benefits of participation by disadvantaged groups	Range and numbers of disadvantaged groups included in participatory management practices, activities and interventions; sense of empowerment; perception of ability to participate; change in confidence
	Organisational cohesion	Solidarity among members; mutual trust and co-operation; capacity for self-management
	Community cohesion	Social connectedness; perceptions of stakeholder groups; tolerance of local differences
	Integration of disadvantaged groups	Accessibility and use of activities, services and products developed by the social economy entity; official recognition of disadvantage factors in the public system; reduced dependency on welfare transfers; improved access to public health, education and other basic services
WELL-BEING AND COMMUNITY	Physical and mental health	Self-esteem and motivation, psychological status (decrease in depressive symptoms, reduced sense of anxiety and isolation); active lifestyle; behavioural changes (e.g., respite from street life); savings in public health expenditures
	Psycho-social well-being	Improvements in living conditions; reported improvements in quality of life, level of optimism, and life and job satisfaction
	Community embeddedness	New relationships created locally; greater interaction of disadvantaged groups with the community; sense of belonging; sense of pride in community; social recognition; collaboration and partnership with other social economy entities
	Political participation, also referred to as democratic impact	Access to policy makers; confidence to contribute and make a difference; changes occurring in the quality or intensity of citizen participation, the modalities of public debate and decision-making
	Environmental quality	Exposure to loud noise, air pollution, or chemical products

Source: OECD 2024

- GreenDelta's PSILCA contains information on 69 qualitative and quantitative social aspects addressing 33 subcategories (see chapter 4.1.2).
- The EC defined a total of 11 social impact indicators (Bührer et al.(2022):
 - 1) Employment and labour markets;
 - 2) Standards and rights related to job quality;
 - 3) Social inclusion and protection of particular groups;
 - 4) Gender equality and equal opportunities/non-discrimination;

- 5) Individuals, private and family life and the protection of personal data;
- 6) Governance, participation, good administration and access to justice, media and ethics;
- 7) Public health and safety;
- 8) Crime, terrorism and security;
- 9) Access to and effects on social protection, health and educational system;
- 10) Culture;
- 11) Social impacts in third countries;

➤ Rodrigues and Rituerto (2022) mention 19 social indicators on macro-, meso- and micro-level (see [Table 2](#)).

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Table 2: Social indicators

Level	Dimension	Indicators
<i>Macro level</i>	Industry	Extent of job polarisation driven by digital skills and job automation.
	Trends	Number of lives saved increase/decrease in life expectancy
	Governability	Threats to democracy. Open government applications.
<i>Meso level</i>	Health	Diffusion of health monitoring tools.
	Industry	Extent of job polarisation driven by digital skills and job automation.
	Equal treatment & access	Households with using a broadband connections-urban and rural. Level of Internet access for households.
	Social inclusion	Digital exclusion.
	Jobs	Effects on health or security of workers. Jobs at risk from automatisation
	Civic engagement and governances	Exposure to disinformation online. Percentage of individuals who used Internet for interaction with public authorities.
<i>Micro level</i>	Health	Overuse of internet.
	Education and Skills	Digital skills gap, digital resources at school, digital skills gap, online education.
	Work-life balance	Tele-working and job stress.
	Social connections	Children experience cyberbullying and harassment.

Personal security	Data protection concerns. Device compromises. Identity fraud.
Subjective Well-being	Causal effect of internet use on subjective well-being.

Source: **Rodrigues and Rituerto (2022)**

- In addition, the EC has defined 12 indicators for the assessment of social impact of new trade agreements on country level (Melim-McLeod et al. (2022).

3 Social Impact Assessment

3.1 Logical structure of a Social Impact Assessment

The social impact assessment is structured along a **logic model** consisting out of specific stakeholder categories, social impact categories, respective subcategories and measurable social impact indicators all interrelated as shown in following [Figure 1: Figure 1:](#).

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Figure 1: Logical structure of a Social Impact Assessment

Source: Own illustration

3.2 Methodologies for Social Impact Assessment

The commonly applied methodologies for social sustainability impact assessment include Socio Economic Impact Assessment (**SEIA**), Social Impact Assessment (**SIA**) and Social Life Cycle Analysis (**S-LCA**). These methods are explained in more detail in the following section.

3.2.1 SEIA

Along Rafiaani et al. (2018) and Rodrigues and Rituerto (2022), **SEIA** is the systematic methodology for determining and assessing the potential social and economic impacts of a proposed development (proposal's/project's/technology's advantages and disadvantages) on local wellbeing, the life of people's families, and their communities as a whole and for various parties. **SEIA** weighs the socio-economic cost against the socio-economic benefit and focuses on the prevention of costs or adverse impact. **This study** also provides how to maximize the beneficial impacts of a proposed development or project.

Rodrigues and Rituerto (2022) describe a **SEIA** methodology for new and emerging technologies. They presented a conceptual framework including the processes of analyzing, monitoring, and managing the intended and unintended social and economic consequences, both

positive and negative, of planned interventions and any social change processes invoked by those interventions (see [Figure 1](#)~~Figure 2~~[Figure 2](#)).

For doing so, the above-mentioned authors recommend a five-step approach:

- Step 1: **Scoping & planning:** Considerations of the SIA and required information or knowledge.
- Step 2: **Scenario development:** Stimulate thinking about possible occurrences, assumptions related to these occurrences, possible socio-economic opportunities and risks, and courses of action.
- Step 3: **Impact definition:** Identify and consider all important socio-economic impacts of the technology under study, from the point of view of who it affects and their relevance.
- Step 4: **Impact assessment:** Assess in greater depth the magnitude or extent of the identified impacts identified.
- Step 5: (Optional²) **Mitigation:** Identify of mitigation measures and mitigation of impacts.
- Step 6: **Recommendations:** Formulate recommendations after the analysis of the main opportunities and risks attached to each impact.

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² This step may not be included in all SIA, as mitigation itself might not be within the control of the assessment team

Figure 2: Conceptual Framework for SEIA of new and emerging technologies

Source: Rodrigues and Rituerto (2022)

3.2.2 SIA

SIA is the process of evaluating, monitoring, and managing the planned and unplanned social outcomes of proposed action including policies, programs, plans, and projects in a qualitative approach. SIA focusses on ex-ante studies but having a process component as well in the sense that stakeholders potentially being affected by the intervention are involved (Bührer et al., 2022). SIA has become a key tool for many governments and public organizations that must obtain precise results for decision-making (Alomoto et al. (2022).

3.2.3 S-LCA

S-LCA differs from other social impact assessment techniques by its object: "Products or services and their life cycle", by its scope: "the entire life

cycle", by systematic: "systematic process of collecting and reporting about social benefits and impacts across the entire life cycle".

In this regard, various **S-LCA** methods have been developed in recent years. The distinction of the different S-LCA approaches is based on the types of data used - which may be of three types:

- Quantitative,
- Semi-quantitative (yes/no or rating scale responses),
- Qualitative.

Thus, the choice of the S-LCA method can affect the result depending on the different evaluation systems.

Moreover, **S-LCA** is aligned to **ISO 14004** principles similar to a E-LCA as it follows the four-step procedure of a E-LCA (from extraction and processing of raw materials, manufacturing, distribution, use, reuse, maintenance, and recycling) providing complementary impact information (social) to the environmental information of a LCA. The need of sufficient data for background (or generic) processes, as well as for foreground (or system-specific) processes, determined that E-LCA studies have traditionally been **ex-post analyses** of well-defined systems (Cucurachi et al. (2018).

Both assessments (E-LCA and S-LCA) use a **Functional Unit** (FU) to define the product system.

Along Rebolledo-Leiva et al. (2023), impact assessment in S-LCA (or Social Life Cycle Impact Assessment - **sLCIA**) comprises the following three steps approach along ISO 14004 framework:

- Impact categories selection and characterization methods and models;
- Association inventory data to sLCIA subcategories (classification)
- Determination of subcategory indicator results (characterization).

Moreover, **sLCIA** comprises the following two methods:

- The Reference Scale Approach (Type I): Uses specific reference points of an expected activity (called performance reference point - PRPs); Type I assesses performances, and collected data is compared with performance reference points (e.g. the number of hours worked per worker weekly is compared with statutory working time).
- The Impact Pathway Approach (Type II): Considers a causal relationship between the organization product system/activities and the resulting potential impacts. In type II LCIA, researchers or practitioners consider the link between two or more phenomena or

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  Subtitle 1.1
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Title 2
  Subtitle 2.1
    a)
      -
    b)
      -
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If you want to use arrows or points, in relation with the example, you would change the letters for arrows.

events in the assessment (e.g. the use of an input or the exposure to certain working conditions in a production process and health impacts on workers).

S-LCA considers the involvement of stakeholders, due to the importance to integrate their perspective e.g. for the selection of impact categories that make sense to stakeholders concerned. Along Yang et al. (2020), also for the decision-making process is the involvement of stakeholders in S-LCA important for identifying and reducing the social hotspots along the supply chain.

In order to systematically integrate stakeholders in a **S-LCA** process, Mathe (2014) defined five steps along a **participatory approach** enabling the selection of impact categories that are relevant for stakeholders:

Step 1) Selecting stakeholders,

Step 2) Collecting data (study of social representations) and reviewing the literature,

Step 3) Data collection (by interviews and literature review) is consolidated by a working group consisting of S-LCA practitioners from different disciplines,

Step 4) Discussion of list of social principles and impacts within stakeholder focus group,

Step 5) First, a literature review of social indicators and databases, second, the choice of indicators by the researchers according to selected impacts.

3.2.4 Challenges in performing S-LCA

Until so far social impact assessment has primarily been based on **qualitative information** determined to some extent through expert judgment. In this sense, S-LCA considers a standard arbitrary linear score set to translate qualitative performances into a quantitative assessment for all subcategory indicators (i.e., it translates A, B, C, D scoring into 4, 3, 2, 1 at ordinal scale). This can mask the decision dependency of weighting scheme and cause a high uncertainty associated with quantification of weights (Sawaengsak et al. (2019).

Carmo et al. (2017) have addressed this issue by defining a customized **scoring and weighting approach** for impact assessment in S-LCA beyond the assumption of arbitrary, linearity and equal weighting. This has been done by developing specific value functions for each subcategory and establishing weighting factors for the indicators of each of the stakeholders.

Carmo et al. (2017) proposed a four-step method to handle the uncertainty of scoring and weighting factors of the experts' value

judgment. The weighting factors are always case study-specific and cannot be generalized.

But still, along Sawaengsak et al. (2019), the simple weighted sum approach and normalization technique for single score assessments have been problematic and the final results do not realistically represent stakeholder perspectives due to mis/over-interpretations. Thus, the following exist gaps need further considerations:

- 1) The issues of the scoring system,
- 2) The issues of the use of a weighting scheme,
- 3) Lack of systematic identification of relevant stakeholders.

To respond to these challenges and to address the reliability of social impact assessment results, Sawaengsak et al. (2019) presented a **weighted aggregation method** to evaluate the importance and satisfaction levels of social impact and impact sub-categories using a **cause-effect chain analysis** to identify all possible sources of social problems. The cause-effect chain in environmental life cycle impact assessment (LCIA) can provide a useful structure for the development of a broader sustainability assessment methodology and helps to pursue ultimate scores, assessing trade-offs between different phases in the life cycle and different impacts in an overarching and comprehensive way. In this respect, the establishment of weighting scores for the importance of social aspects can assist in addressing trade-off of social issues to achieve more accurate and reliable impact results and hence reliable value for decision making processes. Thus, the inclusion of expert opinion and stakeholder perspective can better reflect the potential social impact of a product system.

The proposed social impact assessment framework by Sawaengsak et al. (2019) is designed along the following four steps:

- Step 1) Providing the social categories, sub-categories, and indicators;
- Step 2) Measuring the inventory/characterization results of indicators;
- Step 3) Determining the weighting factor at the sub-categories level;
- Step 4) Aggregation of results of performance score at sub-category and social category level

Along Sawaengsak et al. (2019), for obtaining a performance score at the social category level, it is important to aggregate several sub-category scores into a single score. To address this limitation, all sub-categories include data quality scores which are useful for decision making and identifying areas of improvement.

But still, Social Impact Assessments face a general **incompatibility with quantitative measurements** (Carmo et al. (2017) and Sawaengsak et al.

(2019). Hence, **harmonizing the selection of indicators and streamlining S-LCA methodologies** to established systematic S-LCA approaches are missing.

Moreover, common S-LCA were developed for the **ex-post** analysis of products in general, not specifically for biobased products (Marting Vidaurre et al. (2020).

In addition, S-LCA methodologies for **early-stage technology developments** for cradle-to-cradle assessments are still needed (see chapter 4.1.2).

Furthermore, S-LCA is based on the **ISO 14040 and 14044 standards** and thus includes the same four phases as for E-LCA. In this respect, quantitative assessment in S-LCA is additionally challenged by the necessity to use **Functional Units** as reference unit for LCA studies according to ISO 14040 as most of the indicators are difficult to express by functional unit (Tavakoli and Barkdoll (2020)). But as mainly qualitative data is used in S-LCA, it may be difficult to link the results specifically to the Functional Unit.

Therefore, UNEP SETAC and Life Cycle Initiative (2009) proposes to use the following five steps to specify **Functional Units**:

Step 1) Describe the product by its properties including the product's social utility.

Step 2) Determine the relevant market segment.

Step 3) Determine the relevant product alternatives.

Step 4) Define and quantify the functional unit, in terms of the obligatory product properties required by the relevant market segment.

Step 5) Determine the reference flow for each of the product systems high uncertainty of future technology adoption and of real-world social impacts.

On the other hand, Sureau et al. recommend that S-LCA should not be adapted to fit the E-LCA format, but S-LCA should be tailored to explain social mechanisms by considering the (social) nature of assessed impacts or phenomena, implying other variables and methods aligning Type I and II approaches.

In this regard, as several complementary tools (E-LCA, S-LCA, C2C) are currently being used to reduce the error in the results obtained, it is necessary to **unify procedures** by developing e.g. LCA+C2C endpoint indicators (see Figure 3) mentioned by Peralta et al. (2021).

LCA Categories		C2C - Material Health																	
		Human Health							Environmental Health										
		Carcinogenic effect	Endocrine disruption	Mutation capacity	Reproductive .../...	Oral toxicity	Dermatological tox.	Toxic inhalation	Neurotoxicity	Damage to skin.../...	Respiratory tract	Aquatic toxicity	Fish toxicity	A. invertebrate tox.	Algae toxicity	Terrestrial toxicity	Persistence	Bioaccumulation	Climatic relevance
GW	Malnutrition	X	X																
	Cardiovascular diseases					X	X												
	Respiratory problems									X	X								
	Diseases transmitted .../...				X					X									
	Floods											X	X	X	X				X
	Droughts															X			X
OD	Damage to mammals .../...											X	X	X	X	X			
	Skin cancer	X	X																
A	Visual diseases								X										
	Damage to flora											X			X	X	X		
E	...											X	X	X	X		X	X	
	Damage to aquatic flora											X	X	X	X		X	X	

Figure 3: Relationship between C2C and LCA categories

Source: Peralta et al. (2021)

The new C2C+LCA endpoint weighting method suggested by Peralta et al. (2021), provides an environmental, social and economic evaluation in a single procedure. Thus, the evaluation of the full product life cycle (C2C) includes the Environmental Life Cycle Assessment (E-LCA) and Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA). By this approach, the complexity of the design process is reduced, and the evaluation phases and interpretation of the results is facilitated, without modifying the level of detail of LCA or the eco-effective approaches of C2C. This helps to identify strategies for minimizing and controlling environmental and social impacts.

But further research work is still needed, especially for the development of software (database and calculation tool) that meets the computational needs (automated evaluation to reduce analysis time and cost with LCA + C2C endpoints) to make it widely useable.

Nevertheless, the risks linked to this type of research are related to obtaining quantitative data in the social dimension (Peralta et al. (2021). In this respect, the complexity of social data and the consideration of the challenges inherent in the compatibility between qualitative and quantitative assessment methods are still prevailing challenges.

Thus, the lack of standards, regulations and quantitative assessments means that social aspects are not considered yet enough by companies.

4 Social Impact Assessment in the context of a bioeconomy

4.1.1 State of the art in research

As the environmental awareness of consumers has constantly grown during the last decades, also the demand for environmentally friendly products has risen, too. Innovations that ensure independence from fossil-based resources and enable environmentally friendly production and consumption enjoy in principle high social acceptance in the EU. Technologies and products with reduced human and eco-toxicity and positive effects on the eco-system are considered as important market drivers (Ramchuran et al. (2023).

As bioeconomy is not sustainable per se, its performance must be assessed from a holistic and quantitative perspective, involving not only the economic and environmental dimensions but also the social one. Thus, to ensure that the bio-based economy delivers the expected environmental and social impacts, sustainability principles must be respected and implemented (Ladu und Morone (2024).

The following “**socioeconomic frameworks**” are the most commonly applied in the biobased economy:

- (i) the Global Assessment of Biomass and Bioproduct Impacts on Socioeconomics and Sustainability Project (Global-Bio-Pact (2013),
- (ii) the Global Bioenergy Partnership - Sustainability Indicators for Bioenergy - (GBEP (2020),
- (iii) Oak Ridge National Laboratory - Indicators for assessing socioeconomic sustainability of bioenergy systems - (Dale et al. (2013),
- (iv) Guidelines for Social Life Cycle Assessment of products (UNEP SETAC and Life Cycle Initiative (2009). The UNEP SETAC and Life Cycle Initiative (2009) have provided methodological sheets for indicators and subcategories for various affected stakeholders along the life cycle phase.

However, research about bioeconomy is dominated by natural and engineering sciences, leaving the social perspective underexplored. The social analysis in bioeconomy has been focused mainly on bioenergy systems (especially bioenergy/biofuels production – see [Table 3](#)).

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Table 3: S-LCA studies with link to bioeconomy

Source / case study	Stakeholder	Indicator	Method
Siebert et al. (2018) Wood based products in Germany	Worker, Local community, Society	17 Indicators under three categories	Proposes "RESPONSA" framework following an LCA methodology, by comparison with national sustainability standards
Vinyes et al. (2013) Cooking oil waste management	Worker	11 indicators under six categories	Ignore supply chain hotspots
Traverso, M., Petti, L., Zamagni, A. (2019) U.S. Corn Production	Employee/ Farmer, Consumer, Local and National Community, International Community, Future Generation	18 indicators under different stakeholders	S-LCA and economic cost considerations with scoring sustainability indicators
Aparcana Robles (2013) - Recycling Systems in low income countries	Worker	19 indicators under six social topics	Scoring between 0 and 1 for each indicator
(Mattioda et al. 2020)- Biofuels	Worker, Consumer, Local Community, Society, Value chain actors	-	Literature review of SLCA studies with focus on stakeholders
Macombe et al. (2013) Biodiesel	-	-	Literature review Assessment of social effects of biodiesel production at different levels in LCA
Rafiaani et al. (2018)– biobased economy linked to biofuel	Workers, society, consumers, local community, and value chain actors	Indicators under 10 themes	
Falcone et al. (2019), biobased products	Workers, consumers, local community, value chain actors, and general society	17 indicators linked to 15 subcategories	S-LCA on biobased products
Sawaengsak et al. (2019) – bioenergy	Cane Workers, Can growers, Sugar factory workers, Ethanol factory workers	25 indicators linked to 14 subcategories	sLCIA
Cadena et al. (2019) - hypothetical glycerol biorefinery installation	Employees, Customers, Shareholders, Suppliers, Local communities, Authorities	36 indicators	S-LCA on production process design

Cecere et al. (2025) - mining industry	Workers, community, chain actors, Consumers, Society	Local Valuer actors, Society	69 indicators	S-LCA guiding the design and development process
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Source: Cadena et al.; Tavakoli and Barkdoll (2019) and own research

Moreover, social concerns of bio-based systems are mainly restricted to employment (job) issues, which although they are relevant to organizational performance, left behind social concerns with wider potential effects on the population (Marting Vidaurre et al. (2020)). Thus, social norms and values, social entrepreneurship, or attitudes of the population, have not yet been taken into account in the S-LCA methodology.

In addition, bio-based systems are a complex web of interactions and collaborations in multi-level perspectives, similar to an innovation eco system. But, along Rebolledo-Leiva et al. (2023), economic benefits generated from the value in bioeconomy transactions are “only” captured by selected groups, implying strong inequalities and imbalances in power relations.

Thus, the success of the bioeconomy will depend on changes along the whole value chain and social processes in which multiple actors (e.g., society, government, science, farmers and industry) will interact (Rebolledo-Leiva et al. (2023)). This is because unlike other products, biobased products - especially those with forestry and agricultural origin - come from land-based systems and thus involve direct interaction of processing companies with land workers and landowners (Marting Vidaurre et al. (2020)).

Consequently, the different actors involved, and their interactions as well as the framework settings make the social assessment of the bioeconomy a major challenge.

Therefore, transparent, generally accepted set of social indicators by multi-actors are needed to allow policy makers and planners to make a comprehensive and unbiased judgment about the sustainability of the biobased economy (Rafiaani et al. (2018)).

However, a simplification by applying scoring systems based on preference values of stakeholders is likely to be subjective and is often associated with high uncertainty and associated trade-offs. Novel weighted aggregation methodologies proposed by Sawaengsak et al. (2019) can help to better address trade-offs. Nevertheless, Social Impact Assessments face a general incompatibility with quantitative measurements and current S-LCA methodologies still include simplified and arbitrary assumptions (see chapter 3.2.4).

This makes a quantitative assessment of social impacts in the Bioeconomy still a dilemma.

Thus, a deeper analysis of social implications in this field, concluding empirical research and the development of refined methodologies (incl. for early-stage technology developments) to enable quantitative assessments are still required.

4.1.2 Social impact assessment of (biobased)products and systems

For assessing the social impacts linked to (biobased)products different S-LCA databases and methods can be used:

1) S-LCA

S-LCA can support the evaluation of products through subcategories such as "Technology Development" to assess if organizations are engaged in research and investments on new technologies. Moreover, although S-LCA gives valuable support to assess social implications of bio-based systems (e.g., gender equality, labour issues, technological development, property rights), the transition requires the attention of multiple dimensions of society and influencing factors (e.g., government policy, regulatory conditions, intellectual property rights, human resources, social acceptance and market structure) (Rebolledo-Leiva et al. (2023).

Falcone et al. (2019) used a financial method for the social performance measurement of bio-based products based on S-LCA approach by a two-step analysis:

- Identify and mapping of relevant stakeholders in accordance with their influence and interest in bio-based products;
- Validation and integration of relevant categories, subcategories and social indicators, through the opinion of the identified stakeholders.

Along Rebolledo-Leiva et al. (2023), for determining the potential social impacts of a product/service system, sLCIA Type I should be used, while whether it is to predict their consequences, sLCIA Type II should be utilized (see chapter 3.2.3).

2) Product social impact life cycle assessment (PSILCA)

For assessing the social impact over the **life cycle of a product** GreenDelta®, developed a **database** called "product social impact life cycle assessment" (**PSILCA**) (see [Table 4](#) ~~Table 4~~), compatible with the software for E-LCA methodology such as OpenLCA® and SimaPro®.

PSILCA adopts a multi-regional input-output database, which includes data from almost 15,000 sectors for 189 countries.

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Social impacts are estimated for each category, by aggregating social risks of all processes within the boundary under study. This database encompasses the impact method “Social Impact Weighting Method” which explains the exponential relationships among impact factors (Rebolledo-Leiva et al. (2023)). PSILCA enables users to calculate social risks based on the initial value and unit of each indicator (GreenDelta).

Table 4: PSILCA database (example for “stakeholders”, “subcategories” and “indicators”)

WORKERS	Child labour	Children in employment, male	% of male children ages 7-14
		Children in employment, female	% of female children ages 7-14
		Children in employment, total	% of all children ages 7-14
	Forced labour	Goods produced by forced labour	Number of goods in the sector
		Frequency of forced labour	Cases per 1,000 inhabitants in the country
		Tier placement referring to trafficking in persons	Tier placement
	Fair salary	Living wage, per month	USD
		Minimum wage, per month	USD
		Sector average wage, per month	USD
	Working time	Hours of work per employee, per week	h
	Discrimination	Women in the labour force (total)	% of economically active population
		Women in the sectoral labour force	ratio
		Gender wage gap	%
	Health and Safety	Accident rate at workplace	Cases per 100,000 employees and year
		Fatal accidents at workplace	Cases per 100,000 employees and year
		DALYs due to indoor and outdoor air and water pollution	DALYs per 1,000 inhabitant in the country
		Presence of sufficient safety measures	OSHA cases per 100,000 employees in the sector
		Workers affected by natural disasters	%
Social benefits, legal issues	Social security expenditures	% of GDP	
	Evidence of violations of laws and employment regulations	Violation cases	
Workers' rights	Trade union density	% of employees organised in trade unions	
	Right of Association	score of ordinal 0-3 scale	
	Right of Collective bargaining	score of ordinal 0-3 scale	
	Right to strike	score of ordinal 0-3 scale	
VALUE CHAIN ACTORS	Fair competition	Presence of anti-competitive behaviour or violation of anti-trust and monopoly legislation	Cases per 10,000 employees in the sector
		Corruption	Score (Corruption Perceptions Index score of the country)
	Promoting social responsibility	Active involvement of enterprises in corruption and bribery	%
		Membership in an initiative that promotes social responsibility along the supply chain	Number of companies

Source: PSILCA

3) GreenZee model

Sajid and Lynch (2018) developed a method (GreenZee model) to quantify the social implications of products through the monetary value perception of these impacts (see [Figure 4](#)).

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Figure 4: The GreenZee Model

Source: Sajid and Lynch (2018)

GreenZee model provides users with a relatively simple approach to translate a variety of qualitative and quantitative social impact inputs (as importance levels) into meaningful and understandable financial outputs (as strength levels).

4) Blended Lifecycle Integrated Social System Framework (BLISS)

Tavakoli and Barkdoll (2020) developed a framework entitled “Blended Lifecycle Integrated Social System” (BLISS) that illustrates the relation among production lines, relevant indicators and stakeholders concerned (see [Figure 5](#)). BLISS is a robust method for social life cycle assessment, which simultaneously considers the impacts of production system, social indicators, and stakeholders. The projected demonstration’s production system is from cradle-to-grave and applies the impacts or the weights of each step (Tavakoli and Barkdoll (2020)).

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Figure 5: BLISS Model

Source: Tavakoli and Barkdoll (2020)

But most biobased industries and processes are in an **early TRL stage**, often only function at lab- or pilot-scale, and process data are only available at

these scales. Quantitative data for the whole life cycle process does not yet exist, making full-market scale assessments difficult.

Thus, Social Impact Assessments of early-stage technological developments of biobased products can only be done as **ex-ante assessment**.

Ex-ante assessment does not predict the future, but it explores the future by assessing a range of possible scenarios that define the space in which the technology may operate (Cucurachi et al. 2018). Thus, to enhance robustness of results and for communication purposes, scenario analysis and uncertainty analyses (as sensitivity analysis) are needed (Laurentiis et al. (2024).

Although recent advancements in literature have begun to diverge from the trend of ex-post analysis of systems, which was characterized by the early decades of LCA practice towards ex-ante assessments (ex-ante approaches for performing LCA of products are mentioned e.g. by Laurentiis et al. (2024) and by Souza et al. (2023)), only few studies have been applied an ex-ante process to S-LCA. These are mainly linked to the production process design stage (Cadena et al. (2019; Cecere et al.)Cecere et al. (2025), focusing on a cradle-to-gate or cradle-to-grave life cycle approach.

Thus, methodologies for ex-ante S-LCA for early-stage technology developments covering the full product life cycle (cradle-to cradle) are still needed (Hüseyin et al. (2025).

This makes an ex-ante assessment of social impacts especially for early-stage technology developments along the life whole cycle in the Bioeconomy still a challenge.

4.2 **Methodology framework for implementing S-LCA in the Bioeconomy sector**

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4.2.1 **General methodological approach**

Fraunhofer ISI applied the following five step approach for implementing S-LCA under consideration of the methodology for performing a S-LCA by Life Cycle Initiative (2020) and for integrating a participatory approach in S-LCA mentioned by (Mathe (2014)) (see ~~Figure 6~~Figure 6)

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Figure 6: Social Impact Assessment - Methodological approach

Source: Own illustration along Mathe (2014) and Life Cycle Initiative (2020)

The **first step** is to define the goal and scope of the Social Impact Assessment, to reduce complexity, e.g. with a view to avoiding an overload with data, which is not relevant for the assessed decision options and facilitate communication and collaboration among different stakeholders. The goal is defined by the overall aim of the assessment and the scope of the product and market segment to be assessed. The functional unit of the assessed product in comparison to reference products in the sense of obligatory product properties is defined by its functionality, technical quality, longevity, recyclability etc. The system boundary is defined by the life cycle stages under investigation. In addition, the geographical and temporal coverage of the assessment are considered.

It is worthwhile to mention that a thorough description of the reference product/technology as status quo is necessary in order to assess the social impact of the innovative product/technology.

In a **second step**, it is essential to identify relevant stakeholders. The stakeholders should be analyzed and selected based on:

- Their interests in the activity,
- Their positive or negative impact on the activity,
- Possible dependencies,
- Whether they can be integrated into the Social Impact Assessment.

By engaging multi-actors in a Social Impact Assessment social acceptance factor can be identified which are of high relevance when bringing innovative solutions in form of new biobased products on the markets. According to research studies major factors that influence acceptance of new technologies/ products are perceived risks and benefits, trust, fairness and personal norms which facilitate the placing on the market of this type of products. In this sense, social acceptance factors reflect needs, concerns, expectations, perceptions and challenges of multi-actors (Baur et al., 2022 and Laborda et al., (2023).

In order to validate and refine the social impact categories and indicators feedback from Fraunhofer experts was received.

In a **third step**, data will be collected, comprising social impacts/subcategories as well as indicators combining a top-down and bottom-up approach. Here it is necessary to define relevant research questions (assessment criteria) related to social sustainability, such as the benefits or drawbacks of using innovative processes or products compared to conventional options according to the product boundaries.

In a **fourth step**, impact assessment will be done qualitatively by involving stakeholder groups through interviews and focus group discussions. Thus, potential social impacts (positive and negative impacts) are to be evaluated, identifying social hotspots. Stakeholders' feedback provides additional insights and perspectives and ensures that the findings are robust and relevant.

In this respect the following scales for impact assessment are used (see [Table 5](#) and [Table 6](#)):

- In comparison to reference technology/product,
- Under uncertainty.

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Table 5: Scale for impact assessment in comparison to reference product/technology

Impact	Definition
Significant smaller	Impact has significant smaller effects
Similar	Impact has similar effects
Significant bigger	Impact has significant bigger effects

Source: Own illustration

Table 6: Scale for impact assessment in terms of uncertainty

Impact	Definition
Dubious	These are impacts that have a very low chance of occurring now or in the future.
Possible	These are impacts that are possible, but not likely to occur.
Expected	These are impacts that are very likely to occur.

Source: Own illustration

As a result of the impact assessment along the two scales mentioned in [Table 5](#) and [Table 6](#) the **social performance** is assessed too, taking into account the following impact and probability dimensions (see [Table 7](#) and [Table 8](#))

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Table 7: Dimensions for rating social impacts

Impact dimension	Potential social effect
Negative impact	Impact has most likely a negative social effect for main targeted stakeholder group
Medium impact	Impact has most likely a medium social effect for main targeted stakeholder group
Positive impact	Impact has most likely a positive social effect for main targeted stakeholder group

Source: Own illustration

Table 8: Dimensions for rating probability of impact occurrence

Probability dimension	Definition
Lower probability	Probability of impact occurrence is most likely at lower chance to occur in the near future.
Medium probability	Probability of impact occurrence is most likely at medium chance to occur in the near future.
Higher probability	Probability of impact occurrence is most likely at higher chance to occur in the near future.

Source: Own illustration

As **social performance** is based on assessing the social effects of the impacts on main target stakeholder group, it is important to assess the **relevance** between input and impact as well. This supports evaluating different viewpoints of stakeholders and the interpretation of results (see step 5).

Therefore, a **weighting** of Indicators per impact category enables a ranking of social indicators per relevance of stakeholder groups. In addition, social impact categories can be ranked, too.

For doing so, we applied a weighting methodology along Tavakoli and Barkdoll (2020) (see [Table 13](#)) which we adjusted to our SIA methodology:

$$\text{Social Index} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} SIn * Wn$$

Si= Social Indices (Assessment of effects of social indicators on the impact category in comparison to the benchmark from 1-3, whereas 1 is classified as low effect/low risk and 3 as high effect/high risk – see [Table 9](#))

W= Weighting coefficient (from 1-5, whereas 5 is most important - see [Table 10](#))

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Table 9: Social Indices Scale

Social Indices	Definition
1	Social indicator effect on the impact category is classified as low leading to potential lower risks in comparison to benchmark.

2	Social indicator effect on the impact category is classified as medium with similar risks in comparison to the benchmark.
3	Social indicator effect on the impact category is classified as high leading to potential higher risks in comparison to benchmark.

Source: Own illustration

Table 10: Weighting Scale

Weighting Scale	Definition
1	Not relevant at all
2	Low relevance
3	Medium relevance
4	Relevant
5	Highly relevant

Source: Own illustration

A core part of the “social risks and opportunities assessment” is the identification of “**social hotspots**”. Social hotspots are either “social risks” or “social benefits” along the following methodology as shown in [Table 11](#).

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Table 11: Social hotspot definition

Social hotspots	Social hotspot definition
Social benefit	Impact is classified as positive in comparison to the benchmark at higher probability of occurrence resulting in potential social benefits.
Social risk	Impact is classified as negative in comparison to the benchmark at higher probability of occurrence resulting in potential social risks.

Source: Own illustration

In a **fifth step**, an interpretation of results will be done. The **interpretation of results** considers social performance, social hotspots and social index fostering or weakening social acceptance by stakeholder groups. Based on this, recommendations will be given to foster social acceptance of the future product which enhances better-informed decision making.

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4.2.2 Applied S-LCA Matrix

Fraunhofer ISI has developed an **S-LCA methodology** as decision support matrix based on the S-LCA methodologies mentioned by Life Cycle Initiative (2020) and by (Mathe (2014)) (Mathe (2014)).

Thus, the S-LCA Matrix serves as analytical decision support tool by applying a **multi-criteria assessment** enclosing:

- 1) Stakeholder categories
- 2) Social impact categories
- 3) Social impact subcategories
- 4) Social indicators
- 5) Scales for social performance and social risk/benefit assessments
- 6) Social Index Measurement

The structure of the Social Impact Assessment is based on a **logic model** illustrated in the following [Figure 7](#) (see also chapter 3.2)

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Figure 7: Social Impact Assessment - logic model (illustrated for stakeholder category "workers")

Source: Own illustration

Based on the logical model shown in [Figure 7](#), Fraunhofer ISI developed a **Social Impact Assessment Matrix** which entails the following information (see [Table 12](#)):

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1. Social Impact
2. Social Impact subcategory
3. Social indicator
4. Specification of RTD project achievements
5. Benchmark (reference technology/product)
6. Stakeholder category
7. Social performance assessment

8. Social risk/opportunities assessment

Table 12~~Table 12~~ summarizes the methodological set-up of the Social Impact Assessment Matrix.

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Table 12: S-LCA Matrix based on Fraunhofer ISI methodology (exemplified for one social impact)

Social Impact design						Social performance			Social risk and opportunity
Social Impact category	Social Impact subcategory	Social Indicator	Specification of RTD achievements	Benchmark (reference technology /product)	Main Stakeholder category affected	Social impact assessment	Probability of social impact occurrence	Social Indicator/ Impact relevance	Social hotspots
Sustainable development	Contribution to sustainable transition of the economy	Up-scaling using state-of-the-art technology	State-of the art-technologies can be used	Established production technologies	Value chain actors	Negative / Medium / Positive	Lower / Medium / Higher	Social Index	High risk / Medium risk / Low risk
...									

Source: Own illustration

The **relevance** of different indicators for specific stakeholder groups linked to specific impact categories, are assessed along adopted Social Index methodology (see [Table 13](#)) by the project partners leading to a ranking of indicators per impact category and a ranking of impact categories. The higher the Social Index, the more relevant the indicators are, the higher the Social Index per impact category the more relevant is the Impact category.

Table 13: Social Index Matrix (illustrated for impact category "health&safety")

Impact category	Indicator	Scale (1-2-3)	Stakeholder group involved	Weight (1-5)	Social Index (SI)	Indicator Ranking/ impact category (in terms of relevance)	Ranking of impact category (median) (in terms of relevance)
Health&Safety	CO ₂ emissions	1	Industry	5	5	1. Toxic effects 2. Contamination 3. Co2 emissions	28/3=9,3
	Contamination with risky material	2	Industry	4	8		
	Toxic effects of chemicals on human health	3	Industry	5	15		
...							

Source: Own illustration

5 S-LCA methodology applied to ESTELLA

The S-LCA methodology developed for the ESTELLA project involves a **systematic approach** to best evaluate social impacts of the recyclable thermoset composite and associated technologies at early development stage along cradle-to-gate life cycle stages.

For doing so, we based our methodology on participatory approach for performing a S-LCA mentioned by Mathe (2014) and the S-LCA mentioned by the Life Cycle Initiative (2020).

However, for technologies under development at a laboratory scale only ex-ante techno-economic and ecologic impact estimations can be performed. Thus, this influences our social impact assessments as well due to data gaps and scaling uncertainties.

In this respect, our assessment is subject to some fundamental limitations in predicting real-world social impacts during early technology development and its implementation. Our assessment is hence based on **qualitative estimations** in comparison to the benchmark's performance.

As data source we used insights from **literature**³, **research results** from WP3-6 and feedback from **Fraunhofer experts** as well as **project partners**. Thus, by this approach social impacts, impact subcategories and social indicators have been defined and adopted to the goal and scope of the ESTELLA RTD project and we were capable of qualitatively assessing the potential social benefits and risks associated with ESTELLA epoxy resin development compared to conventional purely fossil-based thermoset composite. Our assessment thus serves as indication for potential future social impacts of ESTELLA products.

Accordingly, we have applied the following five step approach for implementing a **Social Impact Assessment**:

Step 1) Defining goal & scope

- ✓ **Goal:** Identify social impacts and main **social hotspots** of a recyclable BPA based **epoxy resin** with associative CAN with hemp fibers as recyclable thermoset composite.
- ✓ **Product focus and market sector:** Production of thermoset composites with are recyclable in the EU for the leisure sector (Scooter platform).
- ✓ **Functional unit:** Production of 1kg recyclable thermoset composite as lightweight material.

³ Especially for LCA a literature review was made and used as indication for the ESTELLA product assessment.

- ✓ **System boundary:** From cradle to gate: incl. production: Mixing and crosslinking, curing, demoulding, recyclability of fibres and matrix and energy consumption, excl. raw material extraction and packaging.
- ✓ **Geographical coverage:** EU.
- ✓ **Timeframe:** Longterm (>3-5 years).
- ✓ **Reference epoxy resin:** 100% fossil fuel-based epoxy resin as carbon fiber-reinforced composite (CFRC) which is not recyclable and landfilled.

Step 2) The second step consists of **identifying and selecting stakeholders.**

In view of ESTELLA, relevant stakeholders are primarily producers of materials (material suppliers, chemical industry), end-users (composites applications, end of life companies (waste management & recycling organizations)). Thus, the two most relevant stakeholder groups could be defined: **1) material producers, 2) end-users.**

As ESTELLA product development was at lab scale different assumptions had to be made to narrow down complexities and uncertainties. However, as ESTELLA is about early-stage technology/product development (TRL 3-4), data related to upscaling and market application are missing, and hence stakeholder engagement from industry is limited. Therefore, we decided to engage with Fraunhofer experts with background in sustainability assessment and social sciences and with ESTELLA project partners primarily from applied research (see step 3 and 4).

Step 3) The third step is based on **data collection and validation.** This involves a top-down and a bottom-up approach.

Top down:

First selection of relevant social impacts and subcategories as well as social indicators from literature / reference projects:

- 1) By literature research – especially considering social impacts incl. impact subcategories mentioned by Falcone et al. (2019), European Commission (2024) and Life Cycle Initiative (2011) and relevant stakeholder categories.
- 2) By literature research – identifying social impacts of reference product/technology as benchmark with focus on LCA.
- 3) By project results (input from research results (WP 2-6)).

Bottom-up:

Validating social impact categories, subcategories as well as social indicators by feedback from Fraunhofer experts.

As result of the validation process, the S-LCA-matrix adjusted to the ESTELLA epoxy resin entails:

- 5 social impact categories,
- 10 social impact subcategories,
- 15 social indicators,
- Addressing 5 main stakeholder categories.

Step 4) Social Impact Assessment

According to the results achieved in step 3) social impacts were assessed qualitatively with support of ESTELLA project partners and Fraunhofer experts.

Table 14 (~~Table 14~~) provides an overview about the results of the social impact assessment highlighting social performance and social hotspots of the epoxy resin of ESTELLA in comparison to the benchmark.

Table 14: Social Impact Assessment (social performances and hot spots in comparison to the benchmark)

Social Impact category	Social Impact subcategory	Social indicator	Social Impact of epoxy resin with associative CAN and hemp fibers	Social Impact of fossil fuel-based epoxy resin (as benchmark)	Main stakeholder category	First Assessment	Social Performance	Social Risk/ Opportunity
Health & safety	Human Health and well being	Health and safety effects related to human health based on toxic chemicals.	Occurrence of BPA and VOCs/SVOCs and succinic anhydride in the production of ESTELLA epoxy resin (see Del. 5.2 and Del. 5.3).	BPA is a common precursor in epoxy resin production; it is known to disrupt human endocrine systems and metabolism (toxicity). VOCs and SVOCs have negative human health effects due to their toxicity and carcinogenicity (David et al. (2021). Succinic acid and the anhydride are irritating to the eyes, skin, and mucous membranes (Worberg (2025).	Local community	Toxic phenols and their derivatives as well as VOCs and SVOCs in fossil-based epoxy resins are known to disrupt human endocrine systems and metabolism (toxicity).	Negative impact with higher probability	High risk (Social risk)

Health & safety	Human Health and well being	Human health and safety effects caused by toxic chemicals released to the environment.	Harmful emissions by the production of BPA and epichlorohydrin (Epidian 6) by emission of VOCs/SVOCs used as plasticizers based on fossil resources (see Del. 4.4 and Del. 6.4) but at lower quantity: e.g. epoxidized soybean oil, sorbitol and propylene glycol were used to modify properties and increase of renewable content of epoxy vitrimer (see Del. 2.2).	Negative health and environmental effects due to the production of BPA. BPA is an endocrine disruptor acting on the hormonal system in animals and by impacting soils and water when land-filled deposit is used. Epichlorohydrin has negative effects on human health (carcinogen and mutagen etc.) and the environment (aquatic organisms and plants). VOCs/SVOCs impact the tropospheric photochemical oxidant formation; stratospheric ozone depletion and they pollute the environment (David et al. (2021)). Majority of BPA based epoxy resins are landfilled.	Society	Many trade-offs between different impact categories, and uncertainties in the results. Environmental effects are depending on the quantity of fossil-based chemicals and type of natural bio-resource and the production technic used. But less landfilling of toxic waste. Hemp shows environmental benefits, like soil health improvements, reduced water need, water filtration and no pesticides need (Sativa University (2025)). Moreover, hemp is naturally resistant to disease and pests, conserves water, degrades quickly, is not in concurrence to food or feed and can be used for environmentally friendly industrial	Potential medium impact with higher probability	Medium risk
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Health & safety	Human Health and well being	Human health effects based on CO2eq emissions	Human health and safety based on CO2eq emissions Lower CO2eq emissions: Higher content of biobased epoxy resin (30-38%) through reduction of synthetic catalysts and oils (usage of epoxidized soybean oil as reactive diluent, sorbitol and propylene glycol) and green solvents (like cyrene) and by adding plant-based fibers (see Del. 2.2 and Del. 2.4). The energy required to produce hemp fibers is significantly lower, with a production energy of around 5.5 MJ/kg, compared to 54 MJ/kg for glass fibers (Thandavamoorthy et al. (2025)).	Higher emissions as feedstocks are 100% based on fossil sources impacting ecosystem and human health.	Society	products (Ahmed et al. (2022)). But processing of hemp fibres causes water contamination. Potential environmental benefits through reduction of CO2eq emissions by using biogenic raw materials and epichlorohydrin made from glycerin from biobased sources. In addition, hemp fibers act as carbon storage: - 1.393 kg carbon dioxide is stored per kg hemp fiber (Essel (2013)). The uptake of atmospheric carbon dioxide by the biomass used in biobased materials can have a potential benefit on the environmental impacts of these composites. In addition, when renewable energy	Potential medium impact with medium probability	Medium risk
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						source are used additional CO2 emission reduction can be achieved. Thus, greenhouse gas emissions and global warming potentials (GWP) are reduced.		
Health & safety	Accidents and work related diseases	Health and Safety effects based on a reduced contamination with hazardous/risky materials	The ESTELLA resin utilizes a crosslinking system based on succinic anhydride and succinic acid as curing agents and Dibutylamine (DBA) which may originate from curing agents having toxic properties to human health (irritating to the eyes, skin, and mucous membranes) (see Del. 4.1, Del. 5.3 and (Worberg (2025). The usage of scCO2 and Resin Transfer Molding (RMT) offers safer production environment (see Del. 4.4 and Del. 6.4)	Harsh conditions as well as toxic materials are used as modifying agents for treating epoxy resins (like BPA and epichlorohydrin), and for resin production by physical hazards posed by autoclave technology, through heat, steam and pressure conditions and high levels of trim/processing waste.	Workers	Usage of less toxic solvents (like supercritical carbon dioxide (scCO2) for extraction process), RMT technology is causing a safer production environment and thus less severe accidents. SSbD-principles are applied in the production process.	Potential medium impact with medium probability	Medium risk
Green transition	Sustainable development of society	Contribution to green transition based on	Resin: Depolymerization "solvolysis" is one of the most promising chemical recycling	Chemical recycling of thermoset fiber-reinforced composites is at research status.	Local community	Higher recyclability, lower carbon footprint and lower toxic waste generation of ESTELLA	Potential positive impact with higher probability	Low risk (social benefit)

recycling
technologies

method (see Del. 4.4
and Del. 6.4).

The chemical recyclability of the resin is highly dependent on the type of crosslinker, their concentrations, and recycling conditions.

Thermal stability of the composite's material after chemical recycling can increase or decrease depending on the extent of degradation of the polymer, fibers and their interfaces. RTD results with hemp fibers reinforced composite (PP-resin as thermoplastic polymer) show no crystallinity change after thermo-chemical recycling (Zhao et al. 2022).

Recycling of the ESTELLA epoxy resin only with scCO₂ is not possible, solvents (amine-based) have to be added (see Del 4.4.)

However, a disadvantage is the strong dependence of the solvent on the chemical structure of the polymer. In addition, often solvents classified as hazardous or toxic are used and high temperatures or pressures are necessary for depolymerization (Seiler et al. (2021).

epoxy resin, resulting in less landfilling.

But best recycling technic still needs to be developed, as e.g. the usage of solvolysis is costly and causes significant environmental impacts, in addition biodegradability has not been achieved. Thus, more research has to be spent as recycling methods of ESTELLA epoxy resin is not yet efficient and sustainable enough and not yet scalable.

Chemical recycling of ESTELLA epoxy resin could achieve a dissolution of up to 70% (see Del 4.4). Inserting 15-30% of recycled resins different effects on tensile strength and elongation are shown (see Del 4.2).

Mechanical recyclability of the resin by grinding and injection moulding (6 recycling steps) of PP resin with hemp fibers show no change in tensile strength and modulus changes (Zhao et al. 2022).

ESTELLA resin shows mechanical recyclability by cutting and grinding without modifying the chemical structure (see Del 4.3).

Biological recycling of the ESTELLA epoxy resin does not meet the requirements for being biodegradable and therefore not being

			compostable. (see Del. 4.5)					
			<i>Hemp fibers:</i> A fibre biodegradability is achieved from 60-101% based on the amount of glucose released (but no evidence of properties yet) (see Del 4.4).					
Green transition	Sustainable development of society	Contribution to green transition based on upscaling technologies.	Technologies for the production of biobased composites are still at proof-of-concept stage, and still not cost-competitive. ESTELLA epoxy resin can be easily integrated into established epoxy manufacturing workflows by using RTM technology. ESTELLA epoxy resin shows potential cost-competitiveness (see Del 6.4).	The upscaling process is well established, high cost-competitiveness.	Society	Further upscaling and industrial standardization can be achieved by using state-of-the-art technologies like Resin Transfer Moulding (RTM) process. The RTM process is compatible with industrial production due to its closed-mould design, controlled injection, and reproducibility. Although ESTELLA demonstrated the feasibility of integrating hemp fibers in RTM production of composites, RTM process needs to be	Potential positive impact with higher probability	Low risk (social benefit)

						<p>further optimized and standardized for the usage of biobased materials also in view of improving cost-effectiveness. Pre-treatments and strict quality control are required to enhance fiber-matrix adhesion and reduce hemp fiber variability. The usage of scCo2 is only economically viable for high-value applications due to its higher costs.</p>		
Green transition	Market uptake and social well being	Spill-over effect to other industries, contributing to a broader market uptake.	Upscaling & recycling technologies still need to be established targeting higher value products. ESTELLA epoxy resin shows cost competitiveness (see next impact category). In addition, state-of-the-art RTM technology is compatible with industrial production processes enabling spill-over effects (see Del. 6.4).	Broad usage in many sectors and market applications.	Society	<p>When production and recycling process is scaled up and standardized, spill-over effects will be expected targeting higher and lower value-added parts or components. But as still more research has to be spent, a broader market penetration is expected to happen with lower chance in the near future.</p>	Potential medium impact with lower probability	Low risk

Economic development	Employment	Job creation in the European biotechnology and primary sector.	Upscaling & recycling technologies for ESTELLA epoxy resin still need to be further developed. Hemp fiber production costs are comparable to carbon fiber production costs but more expensive than glass fiber (see Del. 6.4). ESTELLA epoxy resin shows cost competitiveness compared to carbon fiber reinforced epoxy resin (see Del. 6.4). In general, biomaterials are currently still more expensive to produce than fossil materials (Andrew und Dhakal (2022)).	High competitiveness and broad market penetration incl. job creation	Society	<p>Although the ESTELLA epoxy resin can be cost competitive under the given ex-ante limitations, additional cost savings need to be achieved by e.g.:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A) Replacing primary cost drivers like BPA and Zinc Acetylacetonate ($Zn(acac)_2$) as catalyst, B) Automation and efficient (local) supply chain management (offsetting higher material and high labour costs for production and processing of hemp fibres, C) Higher renewable energy usage, D) Higher amount of recycled material. <p>As chemicals for hemp fiber production causes wastewater contamination, higher costs for wastewater</p>	Potential medium impact with lower probability	Low risk
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						<p>treatment are needed.</p> <p>This directly impacts cost-effectiveness and market penetration. Due to the need for further cost optimization at this research stage, market applications are more likely to happen first in niche markets that justify higher costs (value-added pyramid model).</p>		
Economic development	Supplier relations	Contribution to economic resilience based local on supply chains.	Potential of establishing more sustainable local /regional supply chains based on agricultural producers and processors for hemp fibers and biotech companies for bio-chemicals etc. (Andrew and Dhakal (2022)	Global supply chains based on fossil resources and chemicals.	Value chain and actors	Hemp cultivation and processing as well as biotech sector are well established in the EU. When the upscaling challenges have been overcome (textile uniformity and treatment) Business models (BM) relying on local supply chains can be established and an increased autonomy in key strategic value chains for resilience industry	Potential medium impact with lower probability	Low risk

						results can be achieved. This will potentially contribute to supply chain resilience and less logistic costs which can act as Value Proposition of BM.		
Economic development	Rural development	Rural-to-urban migration	ESTELLA contributes to keep the capacity of rural areas to provide the services and fulfil the needs of the rural population. When hemp and other biobased material are needed, rural areas can profit contributing to rural development (Andrew and Dhakal (2022)).	Extraction of fossil resources generates jobs, however these are often limited by time. Moreover, there is the risk, that rural areas become dependent from one single industry. Next to this, impacts on land degeneration, water contamination and air pollution exist effecting rural areas (Karduri (2023)).	Local community	Hemp and biobased material production from EU offers opportunities in diversification and generating additional income for local communities in rural areas. But hemp fiber production is not competitive to e.g. production costs in low-cost countries (like China).	Potential medium impact with lower probability	Low risk
Credibility	Reducing uncertainty	Application of sustainability standards/principles.	ESTELLA applied SsbD principles (see Del. 5.3). Due to lack of data, proper E-LCA still needs to be made (see Del. 6.2).	NA	Consumers	SsbD principles are applied to the ESTELLA epoxy resin. E-LCA is a standardized and acknowledged method for assessing environmental performance. Through proper communication, these	Potential medium impact with higher probability	Low risk

						principles and standards can unfold their full potential contributing to further trust building and acceptance.		
Credibility	Participation	Involvement of social groups in the innovation (RTD) process, offering transparency in the decision-making process (co-creation).	As ESTELLA is a RTD project focusing on early-stage technology developments, no major value chain actors from industry, primary sector or consumers were engaged.	Fossil fuel extraction projects have often faced challenges related to stakeholders engagement (Ezeh et al. (2024).	Value chain actors	In order to proceed in the product development key actors from value chain must be involved in the further process. To engage with stakeholder is not often easy as they have different interests and aims.	Potential medium impact with higher probability	Medium risk
Equality	Contribution to justice	Effect on biomass property and use rights.	The use of local biomass (e.g. hemp) can promote equal power relations between different stakeholders offering new (local) markets and empower e.g. farmers to regain control of downstream markets by e.g. adaptation to market dynamics.	Fossil resources (coal, oil, gas) are concentrated in specific regions and to certain suppliers, with the largest reserves found in countries like the United States, Russia, China, Australia and India causing dependencies (National Geographic).	Value chain actors	The rising demand for hemp biomass can strengthen the independence and autonomy of value chain actors (e.g. local suppliers (farmers and hemp fiber and textile producers)) in the EU. This enables value chain actors to become (new) value chain partners. In addition, added value can be created linked to the diversification of income and to soil	Potential positive impact with lower probability	Low risk

							<p>health, carbon sequestration and biodiversity (Shen et al. (2022), see also impact subcategory “rural development”). But as material and production costs of locally produced hemp and its fibers and recycling process of the epoxy resin have still to be optimized, the demand will rather be limited to niche products (long durable and higher value materials at higher prices).</p> <p>For commodity products it is more likely that hemp fibers will be sourced from outside EU (e.g. from China) at lower prize (sustainability vs. prize sensitivity).</p>		
Equality	Contribution to justice	Effects on land use and land change	Potential land use affected when cultivating hemp and lower land use change affected.	land use when hemp and use change	Conflict with land use and land use change and environmental issues exist when exploiting	Value chain actors	By producing hemp potential trade-offs in land use can happen, especially when affecting edible crop	Potential medium impact with lower probability	Low risk

				<p>new fossil sources for coal, oil, gas. Although thermal power stations (coal, gas) and oil refineries have small direct land footprints, they require larger areas of land for their indirect extraction, processing and transportation requirements (King and Benton (2024). This frequently results in displacement of local communities.</p>		<p>production. But on the other hand, it offers opportunities to vitalize marginal areas and reverse land abandonment and it has minor environmental impact than exploiting new fossil sources.</p>		
Equality	Contribution to justice	Equality of benefits and cost distribution.	Potential higher equality in terms of benefits and costs distribution along value chains involving local communities, too.	Inequities in the distribution of benefits and costs. Investors and project developers and local power brokers accumulate the majority of economic benefits. Local communities, especially those directly affected by the fossil projects, bearing the majority of the environmental	Value chain actors	ESTELLA will potentially contribute to equality along value chains when it involves relevant actors in the value chain contributing to the establishment of local supply chains and causing minor environmental and health impacts for local communities.	Potential medium impact with lower probability	Low risk

and health costs
(Karduri (2023)).

Source: Own illustration based on project results, literature study, project partners feedback

In order to assess which social indicators per impact category are of most **relevance** we adopted the Social Index methodology along Tavakoli and Barkdoll (2020) to our S-LCA methodology. Project partners were asked to do the ranking by relevance.

Table 15 gives an overview of results and **ranking of indicators by relevance** per impact category achieved.

A median value per impact category enables us to **rank impact category by relevance** as well.

Con formato: Fuente: Century Gothic, 12 pto, Inglés (Estados Unidos)

Table 15: Social Index

Social Impact category	Social Indicator	Social Index	Indicator ranking/Impact category (in terms of relevance)	Ranking of impact category (in terms of relevance)
Health&Safety	Toxic effects on human health by BPA, Succinic acid and the anhydride and VOCs/ SVOCs	11,2	2	2
	CO ₂ emissions are released to the environment	7,59	7	
	Toxic chemicals (VOCs/ SVOCs, BPA, epichlorohydrin) are released to the environment.	8,25	4	
	Contamination with hazardous materials (succinic anhydride and succinic acid and Dibutyliso-butylamine) during production.	6,66	10	
Green transition	Recyclability of the epoxy resin	12,69	1	1
	Up-scalability of the epoxy resin	12,69	1	
	Contribution to market penetration, spill-over effects	8,74	3	
Economic development	Creation of jobs	3,9	12	5
	Establishment of economic resilient supply chains	5,75	11	
	Rural-to-urban migration	3,74	13	
Credibility	Application of sustainability standards/principles	7,65	6	4
	Application of co-creation process	6,9	9	
Equality	Promotion of biomass property and biomass use rights	7,0	8	3
	Effect on land use and land use change	8,05	5	
	Equality in distribution of benefits and cost	7,0	8	

Source: Own illustration

Step 5) The **interpretation of results** from the previous step four takes into account social risks and benefits fostering or weakening social acceptance by stakeholder groups summarized in chapter 6.

6 Interpretation of results

Results of the ex-ante S-LCA achieved are related to a qualitative assessment of a BPA based epoxy resin with associative CAN and enforced by hemp fibers in comparison to a fully fossil epoxy resin as benchmark. As system boundary a cradle-to-gate approach was applied. Due to encountered complexities and uncertainties in view of assessing early-stage developments, the identification of **social hotspots** faces limitations due to:

- 1) Lack of quantitative data mainly from LCA and e.g. uncertainty about toxic effects due to early-stage technology development,
- 2) Variety of techno-economic assumptions, especially due to upscaling and recycling uncertainties on larger scale,
- 3) Variety of interrelations of impact categories and uncertainty in terms of trade-offs, which account especially for a) environmental effects as they depend on the kind of biomass and amount of biobased material and processing technology used and b) land use as this depends on the biomass quantity and kind of land under cultivation,
- 4) Limited engagement of stakeholder groups esp. from value chain actors (industry) and consumers due to early-stage technology development.

Hence, these constraints limit the identification of potentially further future social hotspots affecting the interpretation of results as well. However, this analysis serves as an **approximation for the assessment of social impacts** of epoxy resin reinforced by hemp fibers on larger scale.

In this respect, **three** potential **social hotspots**, out of them **one** potential **social risk** by the usage of BPA as precursor in the ESTELLA resin and **two** potential **social benefits** in view of *recycling* and *up-scaling potential* have been identified.

“Medium risks” are related to “CO₂ emissions”, “contamination with hazardous/risky materials” and “stakeholder engagement”. Other social impacts are of “low risks” (see [Table 14](#) ~~Table 14~~).

Hence, **social benefits** of the ESTELLA epoxy resin can be increased, especially if:

1. A higher recycling rate of the ESTELLA epoxy resin (preferably from recycled or biobased content from local biowaste sources) will be achieved with impact on:
 - i. Lowering the CO₂eq emissions increased carbon uptake;

- ii. Lowering landfilling or incineration of toxic waste;
- 2. Further upscale will be achieved using standard industrial processes (e.g. state-of-the-art RTM technology) with impact on:
 - iii. Market uptake and spill-over effects;
 - iv. Cost reduction by economies of scale.

Moreover, in order to achieve even **wider social acceptance**, the following should be considered:

- a. Reduce toxic effects on human health by substitution of BPA by biobased materials e.g. epoxidized vegetable oils and of succinic acid/anhydride and SVOC/VOC by the usage of bio-based succinic acid/anhydride and less organic compounds (VOCs and SVOCs) incl. solvent recovery, having a positive effect on human health and the environment;
- b. Usage of renewable energy, recycled material and less-cost intensive processing (e.g. alternative for $Zn(acac)_2$ as catalyst) for further cost reduction and spill-over effects;
- c. Reduce effects on land use when producing hemp by focussing on marginal areas;
- d. Create transparency by applying and communicating sustainability standards and principles (e.g. in terms of CO_2 reduction);
- e. Install co-creation processes involving all relevant stakeholder groups, offering participation and inclusiveness in the decision-making process;
- f. Built up regional/local supply chains to create “value for value” chain actors.

Excuse:

The following **info box** gives a more detailed overview on **risks & benefits** about the second thermoset composite of ESTELLA: “**Epoxy resin with associative CAN with lignocellulose nanofibers from Eucalyptus**” for applications with lower mechanical requirements, based on a literature review.

Info Box:

A) Risks:

Availability of lignocellulosic fibres: The current production levels fall short of meeting the current demand of lignocellulose fibres. The availability of plants that produce lignocellulosic fibres with high cellulose content (which is important for tensile strength) is limited to specific regions based on their environmental conditions (Garriba et al. 2025).

Environmental footprint: Nanofibrillated cellulose-reinforced epoxy composites have a higher environmental footprint in comparison to glass fiber-reinforced polypropylene due to the fact that for the production of nanofiber cellulose from kraft pulp numerous environmentally unfriendly consumables are required for the composite manufacturing process. The environmental profile for nanocellulose extraction showed that the purification process contributes to approximately 95% of the impact. This is attributed to high energy consumption: The production of nanocellulose-reinforced composites is an energy-extensive process, required for dispersion/sonication of nanocellulose in the matrix, resin infusion by external pressure, providing processing conditions (heat, pressure, etc.), post-curing, and finishing as well as an extensive use of chemicals. Moreover, a higher GWP⁴ and a higher abiotic depletion potential - fossil fuel under consideration of a cradle-to-gate LCA boundary has been found (Ilyas et al. 2024).

Intensive monocultures e.g. in Spain and Portugal have negative impact on the ecosystem of native forests when introducing eucalyptus plantations.

Costs: Cost intensive production due to high energy consumption and high costs for catalysts and solvents (ionic liquids) for lignin treatment during processing of natural fibres reinforced polymer composite (Zhao et al. 2022).

⁴ This takes into account the emissions of gas that will contribute to the greenhouse effects (heating effect due to the exposition of gases to sunrays) such as CO₂, CH₄, N₂O and CFCs.

Mechanical properties: The high degree of intermolecular interactions in lignin molecules, can result in poor fibre dispersion and fiber-matrix interactions in natural fibre reinforced polymer composite. (Zhao et al. 2022).

Health effects: Dichloromethane (DCM) used for dissolving lignin fibres having negative effects on carcinogenicity (see Del. 5.3).

B) Benefits:

Mechanical properties: Natural lignocellulose fiber-reinforced polymers have excellent surface quality in molded-part composites and possess favorable mechanical properties, including tensile and flexural modulus. Nanocellulose derived from agricultural waste has demonstrated remarkable improvements in tensile strength and crack resistance, enabling high-performance, lightweight composites (Garriba et al. 2025).

Cost benefits: Lignocellulosic fibres show cost benefits linked to manufacturing expenses of natural fibre composites (Garriba et al. 2025).

Chemical recycling: The recycled lignocellulose composite can be reshaped for the formation of a new resin but at lower mechanical stability/properties (Zhao et al. 2022).

C) Comparison with the epoxy resin reinforced by hemp:

- Nanocellulose has the propensity to agglomerate due to its large surface area. Thus, the processing of nanocellulose and its dispersion in polymer matrices presents significant difficulties.
- When compared to e.g. hemp fibres, nanocellulose fibres are still more expensive to produce, which may restrict its use in commercial applications.
- Less scaling potential of composites with natural fibers from cellulose (less thermal and mechanical properties after recycling).
- Most of the currently available studies on nanocellulose toxicity show that these are generally harmless.
- Low supply of lignocellulosic fibres with high cellulose content.
- Nanocellulose composites have the potential to produce strong, lightweight materials.

Remaining challenges for the commercialization of nanocellulose composites:

- Difficulty in processing,
- Higher production cost,

- Lower compatibility with other materials,
- Low supply of specific lignocellulosic fibers,
- Limited knowledge of safety and toxic effects.

D) General conclusion:

For the production of “truly green” nanocellulose-reinforced polymer composites, it is desirable to reduce the energy necessary for the production of epoxy composites and employ composite manufacturing processes with lower environmental impact. In addition, cellulose sources other than from Eucalyptus have to be explored (best from local waste biomass sources with high cellulose content (e.g. paper pulp)). Due to the lower mechanical properties in comparison to hemp fibers, these composites are more suitable for applications with lower mechanical requirements like packaging or indoor car panels.

7 Conclusions

Our analysis showed that by applying our S-LCA methodology and under consideration of limitations encountered when assessing early-stage developments, **15 social impacts** and **three potential social hotspots** by the production of epoxy resin reinforced by hemp fibres could be identified. Out of three potential social hotspots identified, **two potential social benefits** were detected, related to:

- **Recyclability and up-scale potential.**

The one potential **social risk** is linked to the **usage of BPA** as precursor in the ESTELLA epoxy resin.

Both social benefits are linked to the Impact category “**Green transition**” which was rated by project partners as most relevant followed by “Health and Safety”.

Although a 100% biobased epoxy resin could not be achieved for the applications foreseen in ESTELLA (see Del. 2.2), the results demonstrated advances **in design, cost competitiveness, upscaling and recycling potential** of the epoxy resin.

Hence, ESTELLA showed that the integration of natural fiber and biobased material can help the composite industry become more sustainable and decrease its dependence on fossil fuels (see Del 6.4). This responds to the growing market demand for sustainable products (see Del. 6.1).

In addition, already at this research stage, the ESTELLA epoxy resin shows potential cost and sustainability competitiveness in comparison to carbon fiber reinforced epoxy resins. This offers possibilities to target rather **high value niche markets** (like lightweight products for automotive etc.), which are in direct concurrence to carbon fiber reinforced epoxy resins.

As industrial scale-up and efficient recycling processes will contribute to further cost savings, also other application scenarios are possible targeting rather downcycled applications like indoor car panels or leisure sector (like scooter platforms).

Thus, **further progress** has to be made, especially in the following:

- (1) Scalability of the recycling process in view of achieving the same material quality as output,
- (2) Achieve further cost competitiveness in comparison to carbon or glass fiber reinforced epoxy resins by using automated processes, a higher amount of renewable energy and recycled materials.

Consequently, **further applied research** in close collaboration with industrial stakeholders is needed to address remaining challenges (like

type of biobased material, sustainability, cost-effective production process and appropriate recycling technologies etc.). This applies not only for the epoxy resin enforced with hemp, but also for the second ESTELLA epoxy resin enforced by lignocellulose nanofibers and for the achievement of a 100% biobased epoxy resin.

For all the epoxy resins developed by ESTELLA (but especially for a 100% biobased epoxy resin) it becomes crucial to use (new) plant-based material which are **not in concurrence to food/feed** production (primarily from local waste/sidestream sources and/or from marginal lands) that facilitate cost-efficient and sustainable fiber extraction methods, without sacrificing the quality of the fiber (like from hemp and flax stem or nettle bast) (Ludueña et al. (2013)). In this sense, **local value chains** need to be developed offering diversification in cultivation, environmental improvements (soil health, carbon sequestration and biodiversity), access to new (local) markets and new income opportunities for farmers. This will enhance rural development and supply chain resilience. In this regard, less common biomaterials can create a completely new value chain for the crops used offering direct benefits for rural areas and local communities.

In this respect, the production processes need to be aligned with **industrial and sustainability standards like** ISO 14040 for LCA and SSBd principles to achieve safety and sustainability over the **full product life cycle** (cradle-to-cradle).

Thus, tailored **ex-ante S-LCA methodologies** for emerging technologies covering the full product life cycle need to be developed.

Likewise, in order to make biobased products commercially viable, they need to be timewise supported by **policy regulations** e.g. by low-carbon transition market policies and respective legal acts (like CO₂ pricing, recycling quotes). This will boost the biobased industry to take over biobased solutions as well as the adoption of closed loop concepts. In this respect, the implementation of proper external recycling methods will be supported, too, that can produce reuseable materials by e.g. physical presorting due to the contamination and immiscibility of polymers during recycling stages.

This **policy support** will help to respond to the growing market demand for sustainable products and address social sustainability issues enhancing further trust building and acceptance.

8 Bibliography

Literaturverzeichnis

Ahmed et al. (2022): Hemp as a potential raw material toward a sustainable world: A review. In: *Heliyon* 8 (1), e08753. DOI: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2022.e08753.

Alomoto, William; Niñerola, Angels; Pié, Laia (2022): Social Impact Assessment: A Systematic Review of Literature. In: *Soc Indic Res* 161 (1), S. 225–250. DOI: 10.1007/s11205-021-02809-1.

Andrew, J. Jefferson; Dhakal, H. N. (2022): Sustainable biobased composites for advanced applications: recent trends and future opportunities – A critical review. In: *Composites Part C: Open Access* 7, S. 100220. DOI: 10.1016/j.jcomc.2021.100220.

Aparcana Robles (2013): DEVELOPMENT OF A SOCIAL IMPACT ASSESSMENT METHODOLOGY FOR RECYCLING SYSTEMS IN LOW INCOME COUNTRIES. Online verfügbar unter <https://epub.boku.ac.at/obvbokhs/content/titleinfo/1930544/full.pdf#:~:text=Aparcana%20S%2C%20Salhofer%20S%20%282013%29.%20Applicatio n%20of%20a,Journal%20of%20Life%20Cycle%20Assessment.%20DOI%2010.1007%2Fs11367-013-0559-3%20%28online%29.>

Baur, Dorothee; Emmerich, Philip; Baumann, Manuel Johann; Weil, Marcel (2022): Assessing the social acceptance of key technologies for the German energy transition. In: *Energ Sustain Soc* 12 (1). DOI: 10.1186/s13705-021-00329-x.

Bührer et al. (2022): Concepts and methods to measure societal impacts – an overview.

Cadena et al. (2019): Social life cycle assessment methodology for evaluating production process design: Biorefinery case study. In: *Journal of Cleaner Production* 238, S. 117718. DOI: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.117718.

Carmo et al. (2017): Customized scoring and weighting approaches for quantifying and aggregating results in social life cycle impact assessment. In: *Int J Life Cycle Assess* 22 (12), S. 2007–2017. DOI: 10.1007/s11367-017-1280-4.

Cecere et al. (2025): A socio-economic assessment of an emerging technology in the mining industry. In: *Int J Life Cycle Assess* 30 (6), S. 1349–1362. DOI: 10.1007/s11367-024-02392-w.

Cucurachi et al. (2018): Ex-ante LCA of Emerging Technologies. In: *Procedia CIRP* 69, S. 463–468. DOI: 10.1016/j.procir.2017.11.005.

Con formato: Justificado

Dale et al. (2013): Indicators for assessing socioeconomic sustainability of bioenergy systems: A short list of practical measures. In: *Ecological Indicators* 26, S. 87–102. DOI: 10.1016/j.ecolind.2012.10.014.

David et al. (2021): Volatile Organic Compounds (VOCs) as Environmental Pollutants: Occurrence and Mitigation Using Nanomaterials. In: *International journal of environmental research and public health* 18 (24). DOI: 10.3390/ijerph182413147.

Essel (2013): Life cycle assessment of hemp fibre production and hemp products in Europe - including comparison to other natural fibres. Hg. v. Nova Institut. Online verfügbar unter https://eiha.org/media/attach/1051/13-11-28_Hemp_LCA.pdf.

European Commission: Sustainable Development Goals. Online verfügbar unter https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/sustainable-development-goals_en.

European Commission (2005): Impact Assessment Guideline. Online verfügbar unter <https://www.bing.com/search?q=RACER%20Eu%20Commission%20Impact%20Assessment%20Guidelines&q=n&form=QBRE&sp=1&ghc=1&lq=0&pq=racer%20eu%20commission%20impact%20assessment%20guidelines&sc=12-50&sk=&cvid=FB2C01D1D53C4FF9977BBCB721C09D13>.

European Commission (2024): Measuring social impact: a new era for the social economy? Online verfügbar unter https://social-economy-gateway.ec.europa.eu/topics-focus/measuring-social-impact-new-era-social-economy_en.

European Parliament (2017): Measuring social impact in the EU. Online verfügbar unter [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/thinktank/en/document/EPRS_BRI\(2017\)603930](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/thinktank/en/document/EPRS_BRI(2017)603930).

Ezeh et al. (2024): Stakeholder engagement and influence: Strategies for successful energy projects. In: *Int. j. manag. entrep. res* 6 (7), S. 2375–2395. DOI: 10.51594/ijmer.v6i7.1330.

Falcone, Pasquale Marcello; González García, Sara; Imbert, Enrica; Lijó, Lucía; Moreira, María Teresa; Tani, Almona et al. (2019): Transitioning towards the bio-economy: Assessing the social dimension through a stakeholder lens. In: *Corp Soc Responsibility Env* 26 (5), S. 1135–1153. DOI: 10.1002/csr.1791.

Garriba et al. (2025): Review of Lignocellulosic Fiber Reinforced Polymer Composites for Sustainable Automotive Applications. In: *Fibers Polym* 26 (7), S. 2705–2728. DOI: 10.1007/s12221-025-01007-x.

GBEP (2020): The GBEP Sustainability Indicators for Bioenergy. A TOOL FOR POLICY-MAKERS. Online verfügbar unter https://iinas.org/app/uploads/2021/08/200511_final_WEB_The-GBEP-Sustainability-Indicators-for-Bioenergy-2020.pdf.

Global-Bio-Pact (2013): Global-Bio-Pact Global Assessment of Biomass and Bioproduct Impacts on Socio-economics and Sustainability. Online verfügbar unter <https://www.globalbiopact.eu/>.

GreenDelta: PSILCA. Online verfügbar unter <https://psilca.net/>.

Hüseyin et al. (2025): Empowering sustainability assessment of energy storage. In: *Sustainable Energy & Fuels* (9). DOI: 10.1039/d5se00750.

Ilyas et al. (2024): A review of bio-based nanocellulose epoxy composites. In: *Journal of Environmental Chemical Engineering* 12 (5), S. 113835. DOI: 10.1016/j.jece.2024.113835.

Karduri (2023): Impacts of Fossil Fuels on Rural Communities. Hg. v. International Journal of Engineering Research & Technology (10). Online verfügbar unter <https://www.ijert.org/research/impacts-of-fossil-fuels-on-rural-communities-IJERTV12IS100037.pdf>.

King and Benton (2024): The emerging global crisis of land use. Hg. v. Chatham House. Online verfügbar unter <https://www.chathamhouse.org/2023/11/emerging-global-crisis-land-use/05-land-and-energy-pressures>.

Laborda, Elena; Del-Busto, Felipe; Bartolomé, Carmen; Fernández, Víctor (2023): Analysing the Social Acceptance of Bio-Based Products Made from Recycled Absorbent Hygiene Products in Europe. In: *Sustainability* 15 (4), S. 3008. DOI: 10.3390/su15043008#.

Ladu, Luana; Morone, Piergiuseppe (2024): Sustainability assessments of bio-based products: From research to practice (and standards). In: *Societal Impacts* 3, S. 100041. DOI: 10.1016/j.socimp.2024.100041.

Laurentiis, Valeria de; Caldeira, Carla; Sala, Serenella; Tonini, Davide (2024): Life cycle thinking for the assessment of waste and circular economy policy: status and perspectives from the EU example. In: *Waste management (New York, N.Y.)* 179, S. 205–215. DOI: 10.1016/j.wasman.2024.02.037.

Life Cycle Initiative (2011): Towards a Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment. Making informed choices on products. Hg. v. UNEP/SETAC. Online verfügbar unter https://wedocs.unep.org/bitstream/handle/20.500.11822/8001/UNEP_Life_cycleInit_Dec_FINAL.pdf?sequence=3&isAllowed=.

Life Cycle Initiative (2020): Guidelines for Social Life Cycle Assessment of products and Organizations. Hg. v. United Nations. Online verfügbar unter

<https://www.lifecycleinitiative.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/Guidelines-for-Social-Life-Cycle-Assessment-of-Products-and-Organizations-2020-22.1.21sml.pdf>.

Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment for Decision-Making.

Ludueña et al. (2013): Extraction of cellulose nanowhiskers from natural fibers and agricultural byproducts. Unter Mitarbeit von Leandro N. Ludueña, Antonella Vecchio, Pablo M. Stefani und Vera Alvarez: Formatex Research Centre (14).

Macombe et al. (2013): Social life cycle assessment of biodiesel production at three levels: a literature review and development needs. In: *Journal of Cleaner Production* 52, S. 205–216. DOI: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2013.03.026.

Marting Vidaurre et al. (2020): Social Aspects in the Assessment of Biobased Value Chains. In: *Sustainability* 12 (23), S. 9843. DOI: 10.3390/su12239843.

Mathe (2014): Integrating participatory approaches into social life cycle assessment: the SLCA participatory approach. In: *The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment*, Bd. 19, S. 1506–1514.

Mattioda et al. (2020): Social life cycle assessment of biofuel production, S. 255–271. DOI: 10.1016/B978-0-12-815581-3.00009-9.

Melim-McLeod et al. (2022): EU Bioeconomy Monitoring System indicator update. Addressing indicator gaps: social impacts of trade and share of renewable energy in bio-based industry. Unter Mitarbeit von C. Melim-McLeod, E. Olsen, M. Follador, N. Online verfügbar unter <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/8d92f851-ca44-11ee-95d9-01aa75ed71a1/language-en#:~:text=This%20document%20describes%20the%20progress%20made%20in%202023,its%20current%20status%20and%20future%20outlook%20for%202024>.

National Geographic: Distribution of Fossil Fuels. Online verfügbar unter <https://education.nationalgeographic.org/resource/distribution-fossil-fuels/>.

OECD (2024): Measure, Manage and Maximise Your Impact. A GUIDE FOR THE SOCIAL ECONOMY. Online verfügbar unter https://www.oecd.org/content/dam/oecd/en/publications/reports/2024/04/measure-manage-and-maximise-your-impact_e7b1099d/2238c1f1-en.pdf.

Peralta et al. (2021): Weighting with Life Cycle Assessment and Cradle to Cradle: A Methodology for Global Sustainability Design. In: *Applied Sciences* 11 (19), S. 9042. DOI: 10.3390/app11199042.

PSILCA: Understanding social impacts. Online verfügbar unter <https://psilca.net/>.

Rafiaani et al. (2018): Social sustainability assessments in the biobased economy: Towards a systemic approach. In: *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 82, S. 1839–1853. DOI: 10.1016/j.rser.2017.06.118.

Ramchuran, Santosh O.; O'Brien, Frances; Dube, Nonwabiso; Ramdas, Veshara (2023): An overview of green processes and technologies, biobased chemicals and products for industrial applications. In: *Current Opinion in Green and Sustainable Chemistry* 41, S. 100832. DOI: 10.1016/j.cogsc.2023.100832.

Rebolledo-Leiva, Ricardo; Moreira, María Teresa; González-García, Sara (2023): Progress of social assessment in the framework of bioeconomy under a life cycle perspective. In: *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 175, S. 113162. DOI: 10.1016/j.rser.2023.113162.

Rodrigues and Rituerto (2022): Socio-economic impact assessments for new and emerging technologies. In: *Journal of Responsible Technology* 9, S. 100019. DOI: 10.1016/j.jrt.2021.100019.

Sajid and Lynch (2018): Financial Modelling Strategies for Social Life Cycle Assessment: A Project Appraisal of Biodiesel Production and Sustainability in Newfoundland and Labrador, Canada. In: *Sustainability* 10 (9), S. 3289. DOI: 10.3390/su10093289.

Sativa University (2025): The Environmental Benefits of Hemp: How It Supports Sustainable Agriculture. Online verfügbar unter <https://sativauniversity.com/news/science-and-health/environmental-benefits-of-hemp/>.

Sawaengsak et al. (2019): Development of a social impact assessment method and application to a case study of sugarcane, sugar, and ethanol in Thailand. In: *Int J Life Cycle Assess* 24 (11), S. 2054–2072. DOI: 10.1007/s11367-019-01624-8.

Seiler et al. (2021): Requirements for the Chemical Recycling of Fibre Reinforced Polymers. In: *CHEMICAL ENGINEERING TRANSACTIONS* (88). Online verfügbar unter <https://www.cetjournal.it/cet/21/88/223.pdf>.

Shen et al. (2022): From hemp grown on carbon-vulnerable lands to long-lasting bio-based products: Uncovering trade-offs between overall environmental impacts, sequestration in soil, and dynamic influences on global temperature. In: *The Science of the total environment* 846, S. 157331. DOI: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.157331.

Siebert et al. (2018): Social life cycle assessment: in pursuit of a framework for assessing wood-based products from bioeconomy regions in

Germany. In: *Int J Life Cycle Assess* 23 (3), S. 651–662. DOI: 10.1007/s11367-016-1066-0.

Souza et al. (2023): Integrating ex-ante and prospective life-cycle assessment for advancing the environmental impact analysis of emerging bio-based technologies. In: *Sustainable Production and Consumption* 43, S. 319–332. DOI: 10.1016/j.spc.2023.11.002.

Stephen Appiah Takyi (2014): Review of Social Impacts Assessment (SIA): Approach, Importance, Challenges and Policy Implication. Online verfügbar unter https://www.researchgate.net/publication/303386468_Review_of_Social_Impacts_Assessment_SIA_Approach_Importance_Challenges_and_Policy_Implications.

Sureau et al.: Different paths in social life cycle impact assessment (S-LCIA) – a classification of Type II impact pathway approaches. Unter Mitarbeit von Solène Sureau, Sabrina Neugebauer, Wouter M.J. Achten. Online verfügbar unter https://www.inab.rwth-aachen.de/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/Neugebauer_Different-paths-in-social-life-cycle-impact-assessment-S-LCIA.pdf.

Tavakoli and Barkdoll (2020): Blended Lifecycle Integrated Social System Method. In: *Int J Environ Res* 14 (6), S. 727–749. DOI: 10.1007/s41742-020-00284-z.

Thandavamoorthy et al. (2025): Development of hemp fiber-reinforced epoxy composite with cobalt oxide nanoparticles for fuel cell and energy storage applications. In: *Results in Engineering* 25, S. 103839. DOI: 10.1016/j.rineng.2024.103839.

Traverso, M., Petti, L., Zamagni, A. (Hg.) (2019): Perspectives on Social LCA // Social Life Cycle Assessment in Agricultural Systems – U.S. Corn Production as a Case Study. Unter Mitarbeit von Markus Frank, Thomas Laginess und Jan Schöneboom.

UNEP SETAC and Life Cycle Initiative (2009): GUIDELINES FOR SOCIAL LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT OF PRODUCTS. Online verfügbar unter <https://wedocs.unep.org/bitstream/handle/20.500.11822/7912/-Guidelines%20for%20Social%20Life%20Cycle%20Assessment%20of%20Products-20094102.pdf?sequence=3&%3BisAllowed=>.

United Nations (2015): Social Development for Sustainable Development. Online verfügbar unter <https://social.desa.un.org/2030agenda-sdgs>.

Vanclay, Frank (2012): International Principles For Social Impact Assessment. In: *Impact Assessment and Project Appraisal* 21 (1), S. 5–12. DOI: 10.3152/147154603781766491.

Vinyes et al. (2013): Application of LCSA to used cooking oil waste management. In: *Int J Life Cycle Assess* 18 (2), S. 445–455. DOI: 10.1007/s11367-012-0482-z.

Worberg (2025): Succinic Acid and Succinic Anhydride, S. 1–20. DOI: 10.1002/0471238961.1921030306211301.a01.pub3.

Yang, Sheng; Ma, Kebo; Liu, Zhiqiang; Ren, Jingzheng; Man, Yi: Development and applicability of life cycle impact assessment methodologies. In: *Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment for Decision-Making*, S. 95–124.

Zhao et al. (2022): Recycling of natural fiber composites: Challenges and opportunities. In: *Resources, Conservation and Recycling* 177, S. 105962. DOI: 10.1016/j.resconrec.2021.105962.